

Stock Portfolio Construction Using the Mean- Semivariance Method with Portfolio Performance Measurement and Value At Risk

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Corresponding Author: Yuciana Wilandari	Stock price movements that fluctuate require investors to build a portfolio in order to obtain optimal returns with measurable risk. One group of stocks that is interesting to analyze is those included in the SRI-KEHATI Index, which consists of 25 companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange that are selected based on financial performance as well as their commitment to environmental, social, and governance sustainability principles. This study aims to determine the most optimal combination of stocks from the index using the Mean-Semivariance method, which is a portfolio optimization method that measures risk only from the possibility of losses. The data used in this study are daily closing stock prices during the period from June 2, 2025 to November 28, 2025. Portfolio performance is evaluated using the Sharpe Ratio with the risk-free rate represented by the BI Rate that has been converted into daily return, while the potential maximum loss is measured using Value at Risk (VaR) through the historical simulation method at a 95% confidence level with a one-day holding period. The results show that the selected combination of stocks from the SRI-KEHATI Index is able to generate an expected return of 0.00177 with a semivariance risk level of 0.000111, and produces a Sharpe Ratio value of 0.148247, indicating excess return relative to the risk taken. The Value at Risk calculation shows a potential maximum loss of Rp1,825,374.16 from an investment of Rp100,000,000.00. Based on these results, the stocks selected in the investment combination are INTP, SSMS, and UNTR.
KEYWORDS: Optimal portofolio, Men-Semivariance, Sharpe ratio, Value at Risk, SRI-KEHATI Index	

I. INTRODUCTION

The capital market plays an important role in the financial system as a platform for trading long-term financial instruments, including debt securities and equity issued by the government and private sector (Sumardi & Suharyono, 2020). Transactions are conducted through the stock exchange, which connects parties who need funds with those who have excess funds. One of the most popular instruments is stocks, as they offer relatively high return potential. Stocks represent ownership in a company, allowing investors to claim a share of profits and assets based on their ownership proportion (Darmadji & Fakhruddin, 2001).

Modern portfolio theory introduced by Markowitz (1959) uses the Mean-Variance approach to measure risk through variance. This approach considers all deviations as risk, even though investors are more concerned about downside risk. The Mean-Semivariance model was later developed to measure downside risk, making risk analysis more relevant to investment conditions. In addition, the trend of sustainable investment has increased attention toward stocks included in the SRI-KEHATI index, which represents companies with

strong financial performance and good sustainability commitments.

Several previous studies have examined portfolio construction and evaluation using similar approaches. Pakungwati et al. (2024) applied the Mean-Semivariance method to construct an optimal portfolio of stock mutual funds listed in the Barometer Bareksa and used the Sharpe Ratio to evaluate portfolio performance. Nabila (2023) applied the Mean-Semivariance approach to stocks included in the IDX30 index for the 2022 period and evaluated performance using the Sharpe Ratio. Meanwhile, Gubu et al. (2023) used the Historical Simulation method to calculate Value at Risk for a portfolio of financial sector stocks in the IDXFİNANCE index as part of risk analysis in diversification strategies.

This study aims to construct an optimal portfolio of SRI-KEHATI stocks for the period from June 2, 2025, to November 28, 2025, using the Mean-Semivariance approach. It also evaluates portfolio performance using the Sharpe Ratio and measures potential losses using the Historical Simulation method. This research provides empirical contributions

regarding the effectiveness of diversification in sustainability-based stocks in Indonesia.

II. LITERATUREREVIEW

Investment is the allocation of funds at the present time with the aim of obtaining profits in the future (Tandelilin, 2017). This activity is carried out by investing funds in various instruments such as stocks, bonds, or property to earn returns as compensation for time, inflation, and risk. The capital market acts as a place for trading financial instruments in the form of debt and equity, as well as an intermediary between parties who have funds and those who need funds (Tandelilin, 2017). Stocks are one of the most attractive instruments because they represent ownership in a company and provide rights to dividends and a share of the company’s assets (Husnan, 2015). The characteristics of stock returns and risks, which are relatively high and volatile, require careful analysis in portfolio construction. The measurement of return and risk generally uses historical closing price data as the basis for calculation (Hartono, 2017).

Return is the profit obtained from an investment, either realized or still in the form of an estimate (Tandelilin, 2017). In stocks, returns come from dividends and capital gains or losses. Realized return is calculated from changes in stock prices between periods using daily closing price data. This study uses log return because it is more statistically consistent and economically meaningful (Maruddani, 2019). Log return does not produce negative prices, as decreasing values only approach zero. In contrast, simple return may result in unrealistic values, such as negative stock prices. Therefore, log return is considered more appropriate for financial analysis. The calculation of stock return in period t refers to the formula proposed by Maruddani (2019), as shown in Equation (1).

$$R_{it} = \ln \left[\frac{P_{it}}{P_{it-1}} \right] \quad (1)$$

R_{it} represents the return of stock i in period t , P_{it} is the closing price in period t , and P_{it-1} is the closing price in the previous period.

Expected return is the return that investors expect to receive in the future, calculated as the average of historical returns (Tandelilin, 2017). The expected return of stock i , $E(R_i)$, is presented in Equation (2).

$$E(R_i) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T R_{it} \quad (2)$$

stocks with negative expected returns are excluded from the portfolio candidates. This selection ensures that the optimization process only includes stocks with positive return potential based on historical data.

Risk is the possibility that investment outcomes differ from expectations, and it is measured by the variability of returns (Husnan, 2015). The higher the variability, the greater the risk. According to Maruddani (2019), investment risk can be classified into two types: unsystematic risk and systematic risk. Unsystematic risk comes from internal company factors and can be reduced through portfolio diversification. Meanwhile, systematic risk arises from overall market changes that affect investment returns.

Diversification is a portfolio strategy that combines several stocks to reduce risk without lowering expected return (Tandelilin, 2017). The main idea is to balance stocks that

perform well under different conditions. The effectiveness of diversification depends on the correlation coefficient between stocks, which measures how their returns move together, with values ranging from -1 to $+1$. A correlation of $+1$ indicates no diversification benefit, a correlation of 0 indicates significant diversification benefits, and a correlation of -1 provides maximum diversification benefits (Hartono, 2017).

Spearman’s Rank Correlation is used to measure the relationship between two stocks based on the ranking of returns. This method is chosen because return data are often not normally distributed and may contain outliers. Using ranks makes the results more stable and focuses on relative movement patterns. The Spearman correlation coefficient (ρ) ranges from -1 to $+1$ and is calculated based on rank differences, as shown in Equation (3) (Sugiyono, 2014):

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{t=1}^T (X_t - Y_t)^2}{T(T^2 - 1)} \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the Spearman correlation, X_t and Y_t are the ranks of stocks X and Y in period t , and T is the number of observations.

The strength of the relationship is interpreted based on the correlation coefficient as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Criteria for the Strength of Correlation

Correlation Coefficient	Strength of Relationship
0.00 – 0.19	Very weak
0.20 – 0.39	Weak
0.40 – 0.59	Moderate
0.60 – 0.79	Strong
0.80 – 1.00	Very strong

A portfolio is a collection of stocks held by an investor to achieve an optimal return at a certain level of risk or to minimize risk at a target return level (Husnan, 2015). The expected return of a portfolio is calculated as the weighted average of the expected returns of individual stocks, as shown in Equation (4):

$$E(R_p) = \sum_{i=1}^I w_i E(R_i) \quad (4)$$

w_i represents the weight of stock i , indicating the proportion of funds allocated to each stock, and i is the number of stocks in the portfolio.

Investment weights represent the proportion of funds allocated to each stock. In this approach, all weights are non-negative and sum to one ($\sum w_i = 1$), meaning that no short selling is allowed. The weights are determined using Mean-Semivariance optimization to obtain a combination that minimizes semivariance risk at a given return level. An efficient portfolio is one that provides the highest expected return for a given level of risk or the lowest risk for a given level of expected return (Tandelilin, 2017). From the set of efficient portfolios, the optimal portfolio is selected as the one with the best return-to-risk ratio. This selection is based on the Sharpe Ratio, where the portfolio with the highest Sharpe Ratio is preferred.

The Mean-Variance model developed by Markowitz (1959) measures risk using variance or standard deviation and treats both positive and negative deviations equally (Husnan, 2015). However, investors are generally more concerned with downside risk. Therefore, the Mean-Semivariance model is used to measure risk based only on returns below a target or

expected return, making it more consistent with risk-averse investor preferences (Hartono, 2017).

Semivariance is defined as the average of squared deviations of returns from a benchmark, where the calculation only considers returns below the benchmark, while returns above the benchmark are treated as zero (Marmer & Louis Ng, 1993). In this study, the benchmark used is the return of the IHSG closing price. The semivariance of stock i relative to the benchmark (B_t) is formulated in Equation (5) (Estrada, 2015):

$$S_i^2 = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T [\text{Min}(R_{it} - B_t; 0)]^2 \quad (5)$$

where R_{it} is the return of stock i in period t and T is the number of observations. The portfolio semivariance is then expressed in the form of a semivariance–semicovariance matrix (Zivot, 2015).

$$S_p^2 = \mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv} \mathbf{w} \quad (6)$$

$$S_p = \sqrt{S_p^2} \quad (7)$$

\mathbf{w} represents the weight vector and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}$ is the semivariance–semicovariance matrix. Portfolio semideviation is used as a measure of downside risk in performance evaluation, including in the calculation of the downside risk-based Sharpe Ratio. Semicovariance measures the joint downside movement between two stocks by considering only returns below the expected return or benchmark (Hartono, 2017). Therefore, it focuses on downside risk and becomes a key component in the Mean-Semivariance approach.

According to Estrada (2015), the semicovariance between stock i and j relative to the benchmark is formulated in Equation (8):

$$S_{ij} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T [\text{Min}(R_{it} - B_t; 0) \text{Min}(R_{jt} - B_t; 0)] \quad (8)$$

where R_{it} and R_{jt} are the returns of stocks i and j in period t , B_t is the benchmark, and T is the number of observations.

The semivariance–semicovariance matrix is symmetric, where the diagonal elements represent the semivariance of each stock, while the off-diagonal elements represent the semicovariance between stocks in the portfolio. The form of the semivariance–semicovariance matrix is presented in Equation (9):

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv} = \begin{bmatrix} S_1^2 & S_{12} & S_{13} & \dots & S_{1I} \\ S_{21} & S_2^2 & S_{23} & \dots & S_{2I} \\ S_{31} & S_{32} & S_3^2 & \dots & S_{3I} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ S_{I1} & S_{I2} & S_{I3} & \dots & S_I^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

This matrix is a key component in Mean-Semivariance optimization because it is used to determine the weight vector \mathbf{w} that minimizes the downside risk of the portfolio. For a portfolio consisting of I stocks, the matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}$ contains all semivariance and semicovariance values, which are used to calculate portfolio risk based on semivariance in order to obtain the optimal weight combination.

Portfolio weights represent the proportion of funds allocated to each stock and reflect their contribution to both return and risk. The weight vector \mathbf{w} is defined in Equation (10),

$$\mathbf{w} = \begin{bmatrix} w_1 \\ w_2 \\ w_3 \\ \vdots \\ w_I \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where the sum of all weights equals 1 and w_1, w_2, \dots, w_I represent the weights of each stock.

To obtain the minimum portfolio semivariance ($\mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv} \mathbf{w}$), the weight vector must satisfy two main constraints (Zivot, 2015).

1. $\mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\mu} = \mu_p$
2. $\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{1}_I = 1$ (the sum of all portfolio weights must equal 1)

\mathbf{w}^T denotes the transpose of the weight vector \mathbf{w} , μ_p is the expected return of the portfolio, and $\mathbf{1}_I$ is a vector of ones with size $I \times 1$.

Portfolio optimization can be solved using the Lagrange method, which transforms a constrained problem into an unconstrained form (Manik et al., 2018). The Lagrange function is formulated in Equation (11)

$$L = \mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv} \mathbf{w} + \lambda_1 (\mu_p - \mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\mu}) + \lambda_2 (1 - \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{1}_I) \quad (11)$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 are Lagrange multipliers for the portfolio return constraint and the weight-sum constraint.

To obtain the optimal weights that minimize portfolio semivariance, the function is partially differentiated with respect to \mathbf{w} .

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \mathbf{w}} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial [\mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv} \mathbf{w} + \lambda_1 (\mu_p - \mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\mu}) + \lambda_2 (1 - \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{1}_I)]}{\partial \mathbf{w}} = 0$$

$$\Leftrightarrow 2 \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv} \mathbf{w} - \lambda_1 \boldsymbol{\mu} - \lambda_2 \mathbf{1}_I = 0$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \mathbf{1}_I^T \mathbf{w} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{1}_I^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1} (\lambda_1 \boldsymbol{\mu} + \lambda_2 \mathbf{1}_I) \quad (12)$$

by applying the constraint $\mathbf{1}_I^T \mathbf{w} = 1$:

$$1 = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{1}_I^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1} (\lambda_1 \boldsymbol{\mu} + \lambda_2 \mathbf{1}_I)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \lambda_2 = \frac{2 - \mathbf{1}_I^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1} \lambda_1 \boldsymbol{\mu}}{\mathbf{1}_I^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1} \mathbf{1}_I} \quad (13)$$

λ_2 is substituted to derive a simplified solution:

$$\mathbf{w} = \frac{1}{2} \lambda_1 \left(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu} - \frac{\mathbf{1}_I^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}}{\mathbf{1}_I^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1} \mathbf{1}_I} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1} \mathbf{1}_I \right) + \frac{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1} \mathbf{1}_I}{\mathbf{1}_I^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1} \mathbf{1}_I} \quad (14)$$

For an efficient portfolio based on semivariance without a mean constraint ($\lambda_1 = 0$), the optimal Mean-Semivariance weights are calculated using Equation (15).

$$\mathbf{w} = \frac{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1} \mathbf{1}_I}{\mathbf{1}_I^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1} \mathbf{1}_I} \quad (15)$$

\mathbf{w} represents the weight vector of the stocks, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}^{-1}$ is the inverse of the semivariance–semicovariance matrix, and $\mathbf{1}_I$ is a vector of ones with size $I \times 1$. The proof that the Lagrange function yields a minimum value is obtained through the second derivative with respect to \mathbf{w} .

$$\frac{\partial^2 [\mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv} \mathbf{w} + \lambda_1 (\mu_p - \mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\mu}) + \lambda_2 (1 - \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{1}_I)]}{\partial \mathbf{w}^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{w}} (2 \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv} \mathbf{w} - \lambda_1 \boldsymbol{\mu} - \lambda_2 \mathbf{1}_I) = 2 \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv} \quad (16)$$

The minimum condition is satisfied if the matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv}$ is positive definite, meaning that the quadratic form $\mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sv} \mathbf{w}$ is positive for all $\mathbf{w} \neq 0$. If this condition holds, the resulting

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weight vector w will minimize the portfolio risk compared to other weight combinations. Portfolio performance is evaluated to assess whether investment objectives are achieved and aligned with the investor’s risk preferences. The Sharpe Ratio measures the risk premium earned for each unit of portfolio risk (Tandelilin, 2017). A higher Sharpe Ratio indicates better performance, as it reflects higher returns per unit of risk, while a low or negative value suggests less optimal performance. The Sharpe Ratio is formulated in Equation (17) (Halim, 2003):

$$Sharpe_p = \frac{E(R_p) - R_f}{S_p} \quad (17)$$

with $E(R_p) = \sum_{i=1}^I w_i E(R_i)$ is the expected return of the portfolio, R_f is the risk-free rate, and S_p is the portfolio risk measured using semideviation.

Value at Risk (VaR) is a statistical method used to estimate the maximum potential loss of a portfolio at a given confidence level (Farkha, 2019). The main approaches include Variance–Covariance, Historical Simulation, and Monte Carlo Simulation. This study uses the Historical Simulation method based on historical return data (Jorion, 2011). VaR is calculated by sorting portfolio returns and selecting the value at the α -quantile.

$$VaR = V_0 \times Q_\alpha \times t \quad (18)$$

where V_0 is the initial investment, Q_α is the return at the α -quantile, and t is the time period. The quantile position is determined by $k = \alpha \times T$, where T is the number of observations.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study uses secondary data in the form of daily closing prices of stocks listed in the SRI-KEHATI index from June 2, 2025, to November 28, 2025 (125 observations). The IHSG closing price data in the same period are used as the market benchmark with the same number of observations. All stock price and IHSG data are obtained from Investing.com, while the risk-free rate uses the monthly BI Rate for the period June to November 2025 (6 observations) sourced from the official website of Bank Indonesia.

The data analysis stage explains the research procedures, including portfolio formation using the Mean–Semivariance approach, performance evaluation using the Sharpe Ratio, and risk measurement using Value at Risk with the help of Microsoft Excel. The analysis steps are as follows:

1. Collect daily closing price data of stocks used in the study, IHSG closing price data as the benchmark, and Bank Indonesia interest rate (BI Rate) data as the risk-free rate.
2. Calculate the daily return of each stock and IHSG return, then determine the expected return of each stock.
3. Select stocks by excluding those with expected return less than or equal to zero.
4. Calculate the Spearman Correlation Coefficient and select four lowest values between stocks based on return ranking to identify the strength and direction of the relationship.
5. Calculate the semivariance of each stock based on returns below the benchmark value.
6. Calculate the semicovariance between pairs of stocks.

7. Construct the semivariance–semicovariance matrix, where the diagonal elements contain semivariance values and the off-diagonal elements contain semicovariance values as the basis for measuring portfolio risk.
8. Determine the weight of each stock using the Mean–Semivariance method with a no short selling constraint.
9. Calculate the portfolio expected return and portfolio risk measured using semivariance and semideviation.
10. Calculate the Sharpe Ratio by comparing the portfolio risk premium to the portfolio risk measured using semideviation.

Estimate the maximum potential loss of the portfolio using the Historical Simulation method at a 5% significance level with a one-day holding period

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Portfolio construction begins by calculating the return of each candidate stock using Equation (1). After obtaining the stock returns, the next step is to calculate the expected return of each stock. Stocks with negative expected returns are excluded, as negative values indicate potential losses in the future. Based on Equation (2), the expected return results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Expected Return

No	Stock Code	Expected Return	No	Stock Code	Expected Return
1	ANTM	-0.00106	14	INDF	-0.00035
2	ASII	0.00254	15	INTP	0.00129
3	AUTO	0.00157	16	JSMR	-0.00080
4	AVIA	0.00018	17	KLBF	-0.00212
5	BBCA	-0.00077	18	MTEL	-0.00007
6	BBNI	-0.00021	19	PGEO	-0.00095
7	BBRI	-0.00107	20	SIDO	0.00038
8	BBTN	-0.00003	21	SMGR	0.00043
9	BMRI	-0.00040	22	SMSM	-0.00090
10	DSNG	0.00616	23	SSMS	0.00121
11	EMTK	0.00617	24	UNTR	0.00198
12	ICBP	-0.00198	25	UNVR	0.00329
13	INCO	0.00064			

Portfolio construction is then continued using only stocks with positive expected returns. Stock selection is based on the correlation coefficient to improve diversification effectiveness and reduce portfolio risk. The relationship between stocks is measured using the Spearman Correlation coefficient; the lower the correlation value, the greater the potential risk reduction through diversification. The calculation is performed on 12 stocks with positive expected returns. Before the calculation, stock returns are ranked, and the coefficient is then calculated using Equation (3).

The correlation coefficients are sorted from the smallest to the largest, and four pairs with weak correlation are selected, as they are considered to provide the most effective diversification. Based on the calculation using Equation (3), the selected pairs are AVIA–INTP (-0.23408), SSMS–UNTR (-0.18670), INTP–SSMS (-0.12541), and INCO–SSMS (-0.12178). From these pairs, five stocks are selected: AVIA,

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INCO, INTP, SSMS, and UNTR. These five stocks are then combined into 16 portfolios as follows:

1. Portfolio 1 (AVIA, INCO, INTP, SSMS, and UNTR)
2. Portfolio 2 (INCO, INTP, SSMS, and UNTR)
3. Portfolio 3 (AVIA, INTP, SSMS, and UNTR)
4. Portfolio 4 (AVIA, INCO, SSMS, and UNTR)
5. Portfolio 5 (AVIA, INCO, INTP, and UNTR)
6. Portfolio 6 (AVIA, INCO, INTP, and SSMS)
7. Portfolio 7 (AVIA, INCO, and INTP)
8. Portfolio 8 (AVIA, INCO, and SSMS)
9. Portfolio 9 (AVIA, INCO, and UNTR)
10. Portfolio 10 (AVIA, INTP, and SSMS)
11. Portfolio 11 (AVIA, INTP, and UNTR)
12. Portfolio 12 (AVIA, SSMS, and UNTR)
13. Portfolio 13 (INCO, INTP, and SSMS)
14. Portfolio 14 (INCO, INTP, and UNTR)
15. Portfolio 15 (INCO, SSMS, and UNTR)
16. Portfolio 16 (INTP, SSMS, and UNTR)

The semivariance–semicovariance matrix is used in the Mean–Semivariance approach to measure portfolio downside risk. The main diagonal elements contain semivariance values, while the off-diagonal elements contain semicovariance values. Semivariance is calculated using Equation (5), and semicovariance is calculated using Equation (8). The IHSG returns for the period June 2 to November 28, 2025 are used as the benchmark in measuring downside risk. The results of the semicovariance calculation are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Semivariance - Semicovariance

	AVIA	INCO	INTP	SSMS	UNTR
AVIA	0.0001209	0.0000990	0.0000495	0.0001148	0.0000557
INCO	0.0000990	0.0004157	0.0001116	0.0001062	0.0000934
INTP	0.0000495	0.0001116	0.0002488	0.0000967	0.0000814
SSMS	0.0001148	0.0001062	0.0000967	0.0003602	0.0000709
UNTR	0.0000557	0.0000934	0.0000814	0.0000709	0.0001246

Based on Table 3, a risk matrix is constructed for each of the 16 portfolios. The matrix size corresponds to the number of stocks in each portfolio, namely 5×5 for portfolios with 5 stocks, 4×4 for 4 stocks, and 3×3 for 3 stocks.

The semivariance–semicovariance matrix is then used to determine the weight of each stock in each portfolio. Based on the calculation using Equation (15), the stock weights for each portfolio are obtained as presented in Table 4.

Portfolios with negative weights indicate short selling positions. Since this study applies a no short selling strategy, all weights must be ≥ 0 . Therefore, portfolios with negative weights are excluded from the analysis.

In the Mean–Semivariance approach, portfolio risk is measured using semivariance and semideviation. The smaller these values are, the lower the portfolio risk. The results of portfolio semivariance calculated using Equation (6) and portfolio semideviation using Equation (7) are presented in Table 5.

Portfolio performance is measured using the Sharpe Ratio by comparing the risk premium to the level of risk. A higher Sharpe Ratio indicates better portfolio performance, as it generates higher returns per unit of risk. The calculation is performed using Equation (17) with the risk-free rate defined as the average BI Rate during the study period. The complete results are presented in Table 6.

Table 4. Portfolio Weight

Portfolio	Stock	Weight	Portfolio	Stock	Weight
1	AVIA	53.01%	8	AVIA	91.53%
	INCO	-4.00%		INCO	6.39%
	INTP	13.58%		SSMS	2.08%
	SSMS	-3.74%	9	AVIA	52.64%
	UNTR	41.15%		INCO	-2.26%
2	INCO	3.93%	10	UNTR	49.62%
	INTP	15.50%		AVIA	76.28%
	SSMS	11.77%		INTP	27.03%
	UNTR	68.80%		SSMS	-3.31%
3	AVIA	50.96%	11	AVIA	48.06%
	INTP	12.76%		INTP	12.06%
	SSMS	-3.68%		UNTR	39.88%
	UNTR	39.96%		AVIA	52.84%
4	AVIA	54.06%	12	SSMS	-1.73%
	INCO	-2.24%		UNTR	48.89%
	SSMS	-1.70%		INCO	21.44%
	UNTR	49.88%		INTP	49.53%
5	AVIA	50.03%	13	SSMS	29.02%
	INCO	-3.95%		INCO	5.55%
	INTP	12.87%		INTP	18.88%
	UNTR	41.05%		UNTR	75.57%
6	AVIA	76.37%	15	INCO	6.11%
	INCO	-0.12%		SSMS	14.46%
	INTP	27.06%		UNTR	79.43%
	SSMS	-3.31%		INTP	16.46%
7	AVIA	73.68%	16	SSMS	12.33%
	INCO	-0.08%		UNTR	71.20%
	INTP	26.40%			

Table 5. Semivariance and Semideviation

Portfolio	Semivariance	Semideviation
2	0.000110	0.010505
8	0.000119	0.010925
11	0.000086	0.009288
13	0.000175	0.013237
14	0.000115	0.010710
15	0.000115	0.010720
16	0.000111	0.010529

Based on Table 5, Portfolio 2 has the lowest semivariance and semideviation values, indicating the lowest risk, while Portfolio 13 shows the highest risk.

Table 6. Sharpe Ratio Portfolio

Portfolio	Sharpe Ratio
2	0.144606
8	0.001476
11	0.088254
13	0.069187
14	0.146153
15	0.146954
16	0.148247

Based on Table 6, Portfolio 16, consisting of INTP, SSMS, and UNTR, has the highest Sharpe Ratio and is therefore determined as the optimal portfolio.

The Value at Risk (VaR) calculation using the Historical Simulation method is applied to estimate the maximum potential loss of the portfolio. Daily portfolio returns are

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calculated using the optimal weights in Table 4 based on Equation (4), then sorted from the lowest to the highest value. VaR is computed at a 5% significance level with 124 return observations, where the 5% quantile corresponds to the 6th observation. The return value at this position is used as the estimate of $Q_{5\%}$

Table 7. Value at Risk Portfolio

Portfolio	VaR
Portfolio 2	Rp 1,924,279.88
Portfolio 8	Rp 2,206,870.36
Portfolio 11	Rp 1,329,928.76
Portfolio 13	Rp 2,124,099.64
Portfolio 14	Rp 2,340,742.70
Portfolio 15	Rp 2,175,722.27
Portfolio 16	Rp 1,825,374.16

With an initial investment assumption of Rp100,000,000.00 and a one-day holding period, VaR is calculated using Equation (18), and the VaR results for all portfolios are presented in Table 7.

V. CONCLUSION

The Mean-Semivariance method produces an optimal portfolio, namely Portfolio 16, consisting of INTP, SSMS, and UNTR with weights of 16.46%, 12.33%, and 71.21%, respectively. This portfolio has an expected return of 0.00177 and a semivariance value of 0.00011086.

The evaluation using the Sharpe Ratio shows a value of 0.148247 with an average risk-free rate of 0.000212. This positive value indicates that the portfolio is able to generate excess return and has good performance.

Risk measurement using the Historical Simulation method at a 95% confidence level results in a VaR of Rp 1,825,374.16 for a one-day period from an investment of Rp 100,000,000.00, reflecting the maximum potential daily loss.

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